

TENSILE FRACTURE OF GRAPHITE/EPOXY
LAMINATES WITH CENTRAL CRACK

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Summary

The presented paper investigated theoretically and experimentally the fracture behavior and distribution of the displacement in front of the crack tip of crossplied Graphite/Epoxy laminates with central crack under tensile load.

The displacement field measured by using Moire and speckle methods were agreed well with the results calculated by FEM using isoparametric elements with singular elements at the crack tip. The fracture behavior of three different types of crossplied laminates shown notch sensitivity. The net tensile fracture stress is dependent on the crack length, but the ratio of the fracture stress to the virgin ultimate stress for corresponding un-notched specimen shown the same relation with the crack length for all the three types of the crossplied coupon specimen. The analysis of the failure process and the examination of the fracture surface shown that the splitting along fibre direction and delamination at crack tip were the main characteristics of the crack initiation.

Introduction

Graphite/Epoxy composite materials have been widely used in the aeronautics and astronautics industry. It is very important to study on the stress concentration, the distribution of stress-strain fields and the fracture behavior near the crack tip and around the edge of holes.

Several authors^{[1][2][3]} had investigated stress singularities at the crack tip and obtained stress intensity factors for an orthotropic coupon specimen by using mapping-collocation technique (Bowie, and Gandhi) and hybrid FEM (Tong). Experimental study on the fracture of fibre reinforced composite coupon specimen with central crack and holes had been carried out by other authors (Wu and Mar). Wu investigated the fracture of Basa wood and found that similar to the isotropic materials the stress singularity of the power \sqrt{r} was existed at the crack tip; K_{Ic} , the critical stress intensity factor of mode I, and K_{IIc} , the critical stress intensity factor for mode II, were materials constant and certain relation existed between them. But the study on fibre reinforced composite materials (scotchply type 1002) indicated that with a crack parallel to the fibre direction the K_{Ic} and K_{IIc} were no longer a material constant and the relation between them was not found either. Mar investigated the tensile fracture of Graphite/Epoxy laminates with holes and found the relation between the fracture and the diameter of the holes.

In this paper the tensile fracture of central cracked Graphite/Epoxy coupon specimen with three different lay-ups were investigated theoretically and experimentally. The FEM by using a eight nodes isoparametric elements with the singular elements near the crack tip was used to calculate the stress intensity factor and the distribution of the displacement of an orthotropic laminated coupon specimen. Moire and speckle methods were used to measure the displacement field near the crack tip. The map of equal displacement fringes obtained in the experiment was agreed with the calculated displacement distribution. The experimental results indicated that the net tensile fracture stress and the critical stress intensity factor were dependent on the length of the crack, but the ratio of them to the corresponding virgin ultimate stress were similar for all the three types of crossplied laminates.

Theoretical Analysis

Orthotropic theory^[6] was used in this investigation to obtain the stress distribution at the crack tip. In order to calculate the stress intensity factor and the displacement distribution for a finite size specimen, FEM using eight nodes isoparametric element with singular elements at crack tip was used. For the specimen with a central crack perpendicular to the loading direction, only one quarter of the specimen should be considered, because of the symmetry. In the calculation 52 elements and 185 nodes were used. The results shown on Table 1 indicated that the results of this calculation were agreed well with the results obtained by Bowie and Tong. Fig. 7b showed the calculated displacement distribution which was agreed with the testing results. For the specimen with an inclined crack only half of the specimen was considered because of the asymmetric condition. Linear constraint equations were applied to each set of nodes along $y=0$ so that $u_x(x) = -u_x(-x)$ and $u_y(x) = -u_y(-x)$; and also $\tau_{xy}(x) = \tau_{xy}(-x)$ and $\sigma_y(x) = \sigma_y(-x)$. The results in Table 2, which was calculated by using 96 elements and 325 nodes, agreed well with the results obtained by Gandhi. Fig. 8b showed the calculated displacement field which was also agreed with the testing results.

Table 1 Stress Intensity Factor For Specimen With A Crack Normal To The Loading Line

a/w	$Y=K_1/a^{-1/2}$		
	Result Of This Paper	Tong's Result	Bowie's Result
0.2	1.07	1.04	1.05
0.3	1.13	1.10	1.11
0.4	1.22	1.18	1.19
0.5	1.34	1.28	1.29
0.6	1.47	1.40	1.41

Table 2. Stress Intensity Factor For Specimen With Inclined Crack

	Result Of This Paper	Gandhi's Result
$H_1=K_1/a^{-1/2}$	0.540	0.538
$H_2=K_2/a^{-1/2}$	0.525	0.522

Experimental Procedure

The Graphite/Epoxy laminates were layed up by hand and then cured as 400 mm by 400 mm plates in a neated-platen press following the cure cycle required. The laminates were then cut into strips 36 mm wide and 200 mm long on a table saw using a diamond wheel. The central notch of width 0.21 mm was made by line electrode spark cutting with a hole of diameter of 0.5 mm at the center of the notch drilled beforhand. The length of the notch perpendicular to the load direction was 10 mm and 18 mm. The length of the inclined notch which was 45° to the load direction was 14.1 mm and the projection to the direction normal to the loading line was 10 mm. Three types of crossplied laminates were used in the testing, they were $[0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$,

$[0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/0^\circ]_S$ and $[0^\circ/90^\circ/90^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ and called type A, B. and C respectively. Aluminum loading tabs were then bonded onto each end of the specimen to facilitate gripping as depicted in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 The physical characteristics of the coupon specimen

Fig. 2 Coordinates and two kinds of cracks

In order to increase the surface reflection an aluminum thin layer was placed on the surface of the specimen by vacuum deposition method after the surface had been polished with a grain size 500 waterproof abrasive paper. For specimen with a crack normal to loading direction, specimen grating (40 line/mm) was placed on the specimen surface with the grating line parallel to the crack. The reference grating put onto the specimen grating using oil between them. The fringes occurred as the result of the interference of the specimen grating and the reference grating depict the in-plane displacement of every point on the specimen surface during loading as maps of equal displacement fringes. For specimens with inclined crack, in order to measure the displacement in x- and y-direction, the specimen surfaces were placed by the cross-line grating (20 line/mm) with grating line parallel to x- and y-direction respectively. (Fig. 2) The components of displacement in the x- and y-directions could be obtained from the interference fringes of specimen grating and reference grating with the lines of reference grating perpendicular to the x- and y-directions respectively. Since gratings used were relatively coarse, the speckle method was also used to obtain the displacement distribution at the lower level of load. White light speckle method was used to measure the displacement field. A speckle pattern was first created on the specimen surface which was with high reflection. After putting the photographic plate in close contact with this surface, the specimen was then illuminated in white light as from a flash gun, and a double exposure of the speckles was photographed before and after the application of load. The resulting specklegram is then optically processed using a whole-field techniques. Fig. 3 is a whole field fringes representing contours of vertical displacement of 1/200 mm/fringe. The details of this method could be found in reference 7 and 8.

The unnotched specimen were gaged with strain gage rosette to measure the modulus of elasticity and Poisson's ratio. The testing of the specimen was conducted on an Instron testing machine with the crosshead speed of 1mm/min. Strain and load records were kept via a stripchart recorder or were recorded manually. Fracture load were recorded and photograph of each fracture mode was taken. For several notched specimen 35 mm Movie camera was used to record the Moire fringe and failure process.

Results and Discussion

The testing results for three types of crossplied laminated coupon specimen, type A,B and C were shown in Table 3.

Net Stress and Stress Intensity Factors

Net stress of the central notched specimen at failure were presented at the 6th column of Table 3. The average values of net stress with the same notch length for type A,B and c lay-ups were also showed there respectively. The ratio of this average values of the net stress to the virgin ultimate stresses of the unflowed specimen with the same lay-ups had the similar value provided with the same notch length in spite of the difference of the lay-ups. For example, in the case of $2a=10$ mm, the ratio was 0.575, 0.586 and 0.584 for the type A,B and C lay-ups respectively; in the case of $2a=18$ mm, the ratio was 0.727, 0.776 and 0.753 for the type A,B and C lay-ups respectively. In the 9th column of Table 3 it was also presented the

Fig. 3 u_y Isothetic
Fringes

Table 3 Testing Results

Speciment	Thickness =t[mm]	width=2w [mm]	Crack length =2a[mm]	σ_f kg	Net stress σ_n =kg/mm ²	Everage of Net Stress $\bar{\sigma}_n$ =kg/mm ²	$\bar{\sigma}_n/\sigma_0$	K_{IC} kg/mm ^{3/2}	Everage of \bar{K}_{IC} kg/mm ^{3/2}	\bar{K}_{IC}/σ_0
A-1	1.80	36.0	10	1750	37.39			64.0	64.90	0.984
A-2	1.70	35.9	10	1695	38.49	37.94	0.575	65.8		
A-3	1.90	36.1	18	1650	47.98	47.98	0.727	85.14	85.14	1.29
A-4	1.90	36.1	14.1*	1875	37.81					
A-5	1.84	36.3	14.1*	1575	32.55	35.18	0.533			
A-6	2.00	36.2	0**	4950	68.37					
A-7	2.00	36.4	0**	4630	63.60	65.99				
B-1	1.50	36.0	10	1725	44.23			75.70		
B-2	1.50	36.0	10	1680	43.08	43.65	0.586	73.73	74.72	1.009
B-3	1.50	36.1	18	1710	62.98			111.80		
B-4	1.44	36.1	18	1380	52.95	57.97	0.776	93.99	102.90	1.37
B-5	1.55	36.3	14.1*	2400	58.87					
B-6	1.40	36.2	14.1*	2700	73.60	66.23	0.888			
B-7	1.40	36.4	0**							
B-8	1.60	36.3	0**	4330	74.55	74.55				
C-1	1.80	36.0	10	937.5	20.03			34.3		
C-2	1.90	36.0	10	937.5	18.98	21.04	0.584	32.47	37.04	1.001
C-3	1.90	36.2	10	1200.0	24.10			41.36		
C-4	1.65	36.3	18	615.0	20.37			36.36		
C-5	1.60	36.3	18	817.5	27.92			49.84		
C-6	1.50	36.0	18	810.0	30.00	27.12	0.753	53.10		
C-7	1.55	36.1	18	847.5	30.21			53.63		
C-8	1.70	36.2	14.1*	1050.0	23.57					
C-9	1.60	36.1	0**	2700.0	46.75		0.650			
C-10	1.60	36.0	0**	1455.0	25.26	36.00				

* Inclined Crack Length. ** Unnotched Specimen

critical stress intensity factor calculated according to the following formular:

$$K_{I} = Y_{I} \sigma_{f} a^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

in which σ_{f} was the stress at failure and Y_{I} was the coefficient of the stress intensity factor obtained from the FEM. (For all the three types of lay-ups A,B and C, $Y_{I} = 1.06$ and 1.18 for the notch length $2a=10$ mm and 18 mm respectively.) The average values of the critical stress intensity factors of the specimen with the same notch length for A,B and C lay-ups were presented in the Table as well. Similar to the net stress, the ratio of the average value of the critical stress intensity factors to the virgin ultimate stresses of the unflowed specimen with the same lay-ups had the similar value. For instance, for the three types of lay-ups A,B and C, this ratio were $0.984 \text{ mm}^{\frac{1}{2}}$, $1.009 \text{ mm}^{\frac{1}{2}}$ and $1.001 \text{ mm}^{\frac{1}{2}}$ for the notch length $2a=10$ mm and $1.29 \text{ mm}^{\frac{1}{2}}$, $1.39 \text{ mm}^{\frac{1}{2}}$ and $1.34 \text{ mm}^{\frac{1}{2}}$ for $2a=18$ mm respectively.

For the three different types of crossplied laminates coupon specimen the ratio of the net stress and the critical stress intensity factor to the virgin ultimate stress were similar provided the notch length were the same. This indicated that these ratio was only dependent on the notch length.

Analysis of the Fracture Surface

Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 presented the fracture mode of specimen B-2 and B-3 respectively. Fig. 4 showed the longitudinal splitting in the outer 0° ply of the notched specimen from the crack tip where the stress singularity was existed. Fig. 5 showed the delamination and the fibre pull-out. Also Fig. 6 showed the appearance of the fracture mode of specimen C-6 and the longitudinal splitting in the 0° ply could be seen.

The existance of the notch in the crossplied laminates caused the stress singularity at the crack tip, then made the crack grown along the fibre direction in the 0° ply and formed the splitting. The singularity of

Fig. 4 Fracture Mode
for Specimen
B-2

Fig. 5 Fracture Mode
for Specimen
B-3

Fig. 6 Fracture Mode
for Specimen
C-6

(a)

(b)

Fig. 7 Fringe maps for specimen with crack normal to load line
(a) Measured (b) Calculated

(a)

(b)

Fig. 8 Fringe maps for specimen with inclined crack
(a) Measured (b) Calculated

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Fig. 9 Sequence of fringe maps selected from a Movie film, Load increasing from left to right
(e) Fringe just before failure
(f) Failed specimen

the interlaminar stress caused the delamination and also made the fibre pull-out from the adjacent layers. Just because of the splitting and the delamination in the damage area near the crack tip invalidated the integration of the composites and then caused the early failure of notched specimen.

Analysis of the Map of Equal Displacement Fringes

The maps of equal displacement fringes for specimen with a crack normal to the loading line were shown in Fig. 7; the Fig. 7(a) was measured by using the Moire method and Fig. 7(b) was calculated by FEM. The comparison between them showed agreement with each other. For specimen with inclined crack, the testing result of the component of displacement in the y-direction and the computed result by FEM were shown in fig. 8. They agreed fairly well.

Since the maps of equal displacement fringes represented in Fig. 7(a) and Fig. 8 (a) were taken at the load just before failure of the specimen, it was indicated that for the three types of crossplied laminates mentioned in this paper the analysis by orthotropic theory was valid for most of the area except at the crack tip. This meant that for further study of the failure mechanism and damage propagation orthotropic theory could be used for most of the area and 3-dimension consideration would be limited in a small area near crack tip.

Fig. 9 showed several selected maps of equal displacement fringe from the Movie film of the failure process for a specimen with type B lay-ups. The film also reveal that the failure was started from the crack tip taking the feature of delamination and splitting.

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